

Surface Plasmon Resonance Biosensor with Anti-Crossing Modulation Readout

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Abstract: A novel approach to surface plasmon resonance (SPR) biosensors providing simplified means for an optical readout of biomolecular affinity binding events is reported. It is based on the interrogation of anti-crossing surface plasmon modes traveling along opposite interfaces of a thin metal film deposited on a tailored multi-periodic grating structure. It allows for diffraction-based backside excitation of surface plasmons without the need of optical matching the sensor chip to a prism. In conjunction with low angular dispersion, it enables sensitive and versatile optical interrogation of SPR changes associated with biomolecular binding-induced refractive index variations. Simplified fiber optic readout, as well as multi-channel configuration compatible with regular SPR readers, is implemented with the use of sensor chips prepared by mass production-compatible UV-nanoimprint lithography. The potential of ACM-SPR is illustrated by its ability to characterize affinity interaction of antibodies specific to cancer biomarker CSPG4 on antifouling mixed thiolated self-assembled monolayer with zwitterionic carboxybetaine and sulfobetaine headgroups.

Keywords: surface plasmon resonance, grating-coupled surface plasmon resonance, multi-periodic grating, nanoimprint lithography, biosensor, multiplexing, antifouling biointerface

1. Introduction

SPR biosensors represent an established technology that routinely serves in biomolecular interaction analysis and for the investigation of biointerfaces. It allows measuring the kinetics of the affinity-based interactions when one of the molecules, i.e. receptor, is attached to a solid (mostly Au) sensor surface and the affinity partner, i.e. analyte, is present in an aqueous liquid sample that is in contact with this surface. Association and dissociation of biomolecular complexes at the sensor surface leads to variations of surface mass density and it is followed in real-time by monitoring the respective changes in refractive index without the need for labeling. In further development of this method, among others, two important directions have been pursued. The first relies on the implementation of SPR readout optics to portable devices that can be employed for the direct analysis of target analytes outside specialized laboratories, particularly in the context of point-of-care diagnosis [1], environmental monitoring [2] or food safety [3]. These efforts concern novel instrumentation of miniaturized and simplified setups [4–7] in close connection to research on advanced biofunctional antifouling coatings that are essential for mitigation of nonspecific sorption of abundant molecules masking the specific sensor response [8,9]. The second consists in extending the SPR-based probing of surface mass density changes (that are proportional to refractive index variations) to multimodal sensing systems that combine different bioanalytical transducer principles [10,11]. Such multimodal sensing is motivated by the possibility of studying distinct physicochemical characteristics of biointerfaces and affinity interactions in parallel as well as by the need of improving the sensitivity of the involved sensing principles. Among others, multimodal SPR biosensors were reported in combination with field effect transistor [12,13], electrochemical readout [14], quartz crystal microbalance [15], and vibrational optical spectroscopy such as surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy [16].

Most commonly, SPR biosensors are constructed with the use of attenuated total reflection (ATR) method in Kretschmann configuration that allows for the phase-matching of an incident optical beam with propagating surface plasmon (PSP) waves. In ATR-based SPR biosensors, a disposable optical sensor chip is optically matched to a permanent prism [17]. An alternative approach to ATR-based SPR biosensor measurement that does not require the optical matching has been reported based on disposable fiber optics probes [18]. In addition, SPR with grating coupling element offers a means to avoid the need for optical matching of SPR sensor chips by using diffraction-based excitation of PSPs on periodically corrugated metallic surfaces. These corrugations can be prepared with mass production-compatible techniques and offer a straightforward route for multiplexing of arrays of sensing spots on a sensor chip surface [19]. However, it imposes a disadvantage associated with the necessity of optical probing through the analyzed liquid sample contacted with the sensor surface, which complicates the design of the microfluidic device used for the sample transportation. The possible backside excitation of surface plasmon waves (through the substrate sensor chip from the opposite side to the sensor surface) was reported for metallic nanoparticles supporting localized surface plasmons (LSPs) [20] or, as recently reported, for PSPs on a continuous Au film corrugated with a multi-diffractive grating [21].

SPR changes are evaluated in majority of SPR biosensor implementations from angular or wavelength reflectivity spectra [22]. SPR manifests itself as a narrow dip centered at the resonant SPR wavelength or the SPR angle of incidence and their shifts induced by the changes in refractive index are monitored in time. In order to resolve small changes in refractive index associated with minute SPR shifts, approaches

based on centroid tracking [23,24] and polynomial fitting [23] were applied. It is worth of noting that also other methods utilizing SPR dip width tracking [25], a combination of evaluating spectral shift and shape of SPR dip [26], and conversion to color hue change [27] have been explored for a more sensitive or simplified readout of SPR changes.

In this paper, we report on sensitive tracking of molecular binding-induced changes in refractive index that relies on a tailored multi-period diffractive grating (MPG) facilitating anti-crossing modulation of surface plasmon resonance (ACM-SPR). It serves for backside PSP excitation and allows for spectral interrogation of SPR changes with a non-collimated polychromatic optical beam, which enables versatile implementation to various optical configurations. The performance of the sensor is demonstrated in a multichannel system adapted from regular ATR-SPR biosensor as well as in single-channel fiber optic systems, when applied for the readout of layer-by-layer (LbL) deposition and biomolecular affinity interaction analysis. The processing of acquired spectra featuring two SPR dips with opposite sensitivity to refractive index changes is carried out and demonstrated to offer a resolution comparable to other SPR systems. In addition, it is employed to aid the development of an immunoassay-based detection of cancer biomarker on top of a self-assembled antifouling biointerface bearing functional zwitterionic groups.

2. Methods

2.1 Chemicals

Phosphate buffer saline tablets (PBS: 137 mM NaCl, 10 mM phosphate, 2.7 mM KCl, pH = 7.4), bovine serum albumin (BSA), Tween-20, potassium chloride ($\geq 99\%$), poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (PDADMAC, low molecular weight, average weight < 100.000 Da), Poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate) (PSS, low molecular weight, average weight ≈ 70.000 Da), and HellmanexTM III solution were obtained from Sigma (Germany). PBS-Tween-BSA was prepared by adding Tween20 (0.05%) and BSA (0.1%) to PBS solution. N-(3-Dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC hydrochloride) and N-Hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) were purchased from Merck (Germany). Ethanol (96%) and ethanol absolute ($\geq 99.8\%$) were obtained from Penta (Czechia). Ethanolamine (1M pH 8.5) was acquired from Cytiva (USA). All buffer solutions were prepared by using ultrapure water (Direct-Q 3UV, Merck, Germany).

2.2 Biomaterials

Human CSPG4 protein was expressed in suspension CHO stable cell culture. The cell culture broth was centrifuged, and the protein-rich supernatant was purified by affinity chromatography using a HisTrapTM FF Crude column. After washing and elution with appropriate buffers, the eluted fractions were pooled, and the buffer was exchanged to PBS, pH 7.2. Next, the target protein was loaded onto the HiLoadTM 26/600 Superdex 200pg 320ml column, and fractions with higher purity were combined. The purified CSPG4 protein was subsequently analyzed by SDS-PAGE and SEC-HPLC, determining an estimated molecular weight of ~ 250 kDa. Murine antibodies against chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4-(CSPG4), Ep2 and Ep3, were prepared according to a previously reported procedure [28].

2.3 Preparation of sensor chips

ACM-SPR sensor chips with MPG were prepared from a master structure developed in our previous work [21] as schematically shown in **Fig. 1**. The MPG corrugation profile on the master structure was casted to a soft polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS, from DOW Europe GmbH) stamp by using curing at room temperature (3 days) or elevated temperature of 60°C (overnight). The cured PDMS stamp was detached from the

master substrate, leaving a negative copy of the MPG structure in the PDMS. BK7 glass substrates (1 mm in thickness) were cut to a dimension of 2×2 cm² and cleaned by subsequent sonication for 15 min in a 1% HellmanexTM III aqueous solution, 15 min in ultrapure water, and 15 min in ethanol. Amonil MMS10 (from AMO GmbH, Germany) was spun on cleaned glass substrates at 3000 rpm for 120 s. The PDMS working stamp was placed on top of the Amonil layer to imprint the MPG structure. After a resting time of 5 min, the Amonil layer was irradiated by UV light at 365 nm with a dose of 2 J cm⁻² (UV lamp Bio-Link 365, Vilber Lourmat). The PDMS working stamp was then detached from the UV-cured Amonil layer, leaving a copy of the MPG master structure. The substrates with Amonil MPG were then coated with a thin adhesion layer of Cr ($d_{Cr} = 0.5$ to 2 nm) followed by a 50 nm thick Au layer by thermal evaporation (Plassys MEB 300) with a pre-vacuum of 2·10⁻⁷ mbar and a coating rate of 0.03 nm s⁻¹.

Fig. 1 Preparation of ACM-SPR sensor chip: i) casting of the PDMS stamp with a MPG corrugation, ii) stamp release from the master structure, iii) copying of the MPG to a UV-curable Amonil resin, iv) stamp release from cured copy, v) coating with thin metal films and vi) modification with a biointerface.

2.4 Morphological characterization

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were obtained using a Bruker Dimension Icon set-up, operating in tapping mode and using TESPA-V2 tips with tip stiffness of 42 N m⁻¹ in air. The 5×5 μm² images were captured at a scan rate of 0.98 Hz with a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels per image.

2.5 Functionalization of sensor chips

Zwitterionic carboxybetaine (CB) and sulfobetaine (SB) thiols were synthesized based on the previously reported protocol [29]. Briefly, for the synthesis of SB thiol, 11-bromo-1-undecene was dissolved in THF then added to dimethylamine solution, and the reaction mixture was stirred at 50 °C for 16 h. The solvent was removed by rotovap under reduced pressure. 1M NaOH was added to titrate the concentrated

product, and the organic product was collected and extracted twice from diethyl ether. The organic solution was filtered through anhydrous sodium sulfate and finally concentrated by rotovap to give a clear brown oil of N,N-dimethyl-undec-10-enyl-amine. Then, N,N-dimethyl-undec-10-enyl-amine was dissolved in anhydrous acetone then added 1,3-propanesultone and stirred at room temperature for 2 days. The solution was added dropwise to acetone and recrystallized to get a white powder of 3-(N,N-dimethyl-undec-10-enyl-amino)-propane-1-sulfonic acid. 3-(N,N-dimethyl-undec-10-enyl-amino)-propane-1-sulfonic acid was mixed with methanol solution and thioacetic acid in an oxygen-free atmosphere. Then 2,2'-azo (2-methylpropionitrile) was added to the solution, and the solution was allowed to react for 36 h in a photoreactor at a wavelength of 365 nm under an oxygen-free environment. The resulting solution was added dropwise to anhydrous acetone and recrystallized to get a white powder. The powder was washed with a 1 M NaOH solution and neutralized using 1 M HCl solution. After precipitation in absolute ethanol, the white solid was removed by filtration. The solution was dried to give a white solid of 3-[(11-mercapto-undecyl)-N,N-dimethyl-amino]-propane-1-sulfonic acid (SB thiol).

For the synthesis of CB thiol, N,N-dimethyl-undec-10-enyl-amine was mixed with ethyl 4-bromobutyrate and acetonitrile and stirred at 50 ° C for 3 days. The solvent was removed by rotovap and the solution was added dropwise to diethyl ether and stirred for 10 min. The supernatant was removed, and the product was purified twice to obtain dark brown oil. The oil was mixed with methanol and thioacetic acid in a nitrogen atmosphere. Then 2,2'-azobis (2-methylpropionitrile) was added, and the mixture was allowed to react in a photoreactor at a wavelength of 365 nm for 36 h. The solvent was removed by rotovap under reduced pressure. The solution was added dropwise to diethyl ether for 10 min with stirring. The supernatant was removed to obtain yellow oil. The yellow oil product was dissolved in deionized water under nitrogen atmosphere and stirred for 5 min. Then 1 M aqueous sodium hydroxide was slowly added, followed by stirring for 3 h and neutralization using 1 M HCl solution. The product was dissolved in absolute ethanol and filtered to remove the white solid. The solution was then added dropwise to diethyl ether, and the supernatant was removed. After the final solution was concentrated by rotovap, bright yellow oil of CB thiol was obtained. ACM-SPR sensor chips with a thin Au film were rinsed with ethanol and treated with a UV ozone cleaner (from Jelight, USA) for 30 min. Immediately after the cleaning, they were immersed overnight in ethanolic solution with dissolved CB- and SB-thiols (0.2 mM and 0.8 mM, respectively) in order to form a self-assembled monolayer (SAM). After rinsing with ethanol, SAM-modified Au chips were dried under a stream of pressured nitrogen and stored in the dark with the nitrogen atmosphere until use.

For calibration of the sensor response to surface mass density changes (Γ), a polyelectrolyte multilayer (PEM) assembly was conducted on the bare Au surface following a previously described protocol [13]. Briefly, solutions of PDADMAC and PSS at a concentration of 1 mg mL⁻¹ were prepared in 100 mM KCl. PEM layers were assembled by alternating contacting of the sensor surface with PDADMAC and PSS solution for 15 minutes with rinsing steps in between. This sequence was repeated for a total of 8 layers, with PDADMAC as the initial layer.

2.6 Optical setup

Two optical setups were used for the readout of sensor response on the ACM-SPR sensor chip. Firstly, a simplified fiber optic readout with a non-collimated light beam was implemented with a polychromatic light beam emitted from a halogen light source (12 V, HL-2000-LL, Ocean Insight) launched to a Y fiber optic splitter (400 μ m core diameter, Thorlabs Inc.). The end of the one arm of fiber optic splitter was placed at the backside of the ACM-SPR sensor chip substrate (see **Fig. 2a**) and a polychromatic light beam

cone emitted from the fiber irradiated the sensing spot. The beam was reflected from the Au-coated MPG structure and was collected by the same arm of the fiber optic splitter and delivered *via* its second arm to a spectrometer (HR4000, Ocean Insight). The obtained wavelength spectra were normalized with a spectrum acquired from a reference flat Au surface. Reflectivity spectra were acquired with an integration time of 4 ms and averaging of 300 was used for reducing noise. For calibration of the ACM-SPR biosensor, a regular fiber optic SPR sensor with an optical fiber tip directly coated with a thin Au film was used [13]. The system was described previously and used the same optical fiber splitter, light source, and spectrometer as described above.

Secondly, a multichannel SPR spectrometer was adapted for the readout from two spots on the chip in parallel as schematically shown in **Fig. 2b**. A polychromatic beam emitted from a halogen lamp (HL2000 from Ocean Insight, USA) was coupled to an optical fiber (M25L01 from Thorlabs, UK) connected to a collimator with a lens focal distance of 50.0 mm. The beam passed through two square $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ apertures in order to yield two parallel beams. These two spatially separated beams were made normally impinging at two sensing spots on the ACM-SPR sensor chip from the back side of the glass substrate. The reflected beams were separated from incident beams by a splitter (CCM1-BS014 from Thorlabs, UK) and they were directed towards two optical fibers (FT300EMT from Thorlabs, UK) with GRIN lens (GRINTECH, Germany) at their ends. Each beam coupled to the optical fiber was delivered to a spectrometer (FLAME-T from Ocean Optics, USA) and a custom software FunBIMS was used to acquire the raw wavelength spectra. Integration time of 25 ms and accumulation of 60 was applied. Against the ACM-SPR sensor chip surface, a flow-cell was clamped in order to transport analyzed liquid samples to the sensing spots. It consisted of a module printed using stereolithography (Prusa S11s, resin Prusa green transparent). After printing, the part was rinsed thoroughly with isopropyl alcohol, dried with a nitrogen stream, and post-cured with UV light. Input and output channels of the two flow chambers were connected with input and output tubing Tygon LMT-55 (Ismatek, Germany). These flow chambers were defined by a PDMS gasket, and their volume was $5.6 \mu\text{L}$. The gasket was cut from a PDMS sheet with a thickness of approx. 0.34 mm by using a plotter (Silhouette Cameo[®] 4 from Silhouette America, USA). Liquid samples were flowed over the sensor chip surface at room temperature using a peristaltic pump (Ismatek, Germany) at a flow rate of $30 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$, while washing steps were performed at a higher flow rate of $60 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$.

Fig. 2 Optical schematics of a) optical instrument for excitation and collection of probing light beam with a fiber coupler, and b) two-channel sensor configuration.

As reference optical system, a prism-based ATR SPR biosensor with Kretschmann configuration was used. It was assembled from the same components as the previous system, but the beam splitter was replaced by an optical prism (made from LASF9 glass, 60°) to which a sensor chip, with a flat 2 nm Ti and 50 nm thick Au film (prepared by L.E.T. Optomechanika, Czech Republic) was optically matched with immersion oil (from Cargille, USA). The prism and output optical fibers were mounted on a rotation stage that allowed controlling the angle of incidence θ .

2.7 Data processing

Raw reflectivity spectra acquired from ACM-SPR sensor chip area carrying the multidiffractive grating were normalized with those measured from a reference flat Au-coated surface and saved as a time series. They were then processed by in house written Python scripts. To obtain sensorgrams from the recorded spectra, for every time step the average intensity $\bar{R}(\lambda_i)$ was calculated for λ_L and λ_S by averaging 100 values corresponding to a width of about 8 nm, centered at λ_L and λ_S respectively to reduce noise. The averaged intensities are then divided to calculate the ACM-SPR signal $\bar{R}(\lambda_L)/\bar{R}(\lambda_S)$ and exported as time series.

In reference SPR biosensor configuration with prism coupler ATR method, reflectivity spectra were measured for transverse magnetic polarization normalized with transverse electric polarization with an angle of incidence set to about 42°. The sensor output was defined as resonant wavelength λ_{SPR} , which was determined by fitting of SPR dips with a polynomial function.

3. Results

The implementation of proposed ACM-SPR biosensor was carried out with two optical configurations enabling spectral interrogation of resonantly excited PSPs on the sensor surface bearing MPG. In the first configuration shown in **Fig. 2a**, multimode optical fiber was used for the back-side excitation of PSPs. In this sensor design, a non-collimated polychromatic optical beam probed the sensor surface by positioning the optical fiber tip directly below the glass substrate supporting the sensor chip. The same fiber was used for collecting the reflected beam from the MPG structure and its delivery to a spectrometer. In the second configuration, we implemented a two-channel configuration, where two parallel collimated polychromatic beams are impinging at two spatially distinct sensing spots. These beams reflected from the surface with MPG and delivered to two spectrometers. As discussed further, the sensor chips with metallic MPGs structure were optimized for the readout of minute refractive index changes and the effect of the beam divergence (that smears the resonance in regular grating-coupled SPR) was investigated. Afterwards, the application of developed sensor platforms with the ACM-SPR for the monitoring of affinity biomolecular interactions is demonstrated. The performance of the sensor is compared by performing a readout of the same assay by conventionally used SPR biosensor with Kretschmann geometry of ATR that uses the same optical components.

3.1. Tuning of sensor chips for ACM-SPR

Relief profile the MPG structure was prepared by using a PDMS working stamp and UV-nanoimprint lithography that was followed by coating with a thin Au layer (see Fig. 1). The MPG structure is designed as overlaid sinusoidal corrugations with long-period (Λ_1) and short-period (Λ_2) components. These corrugations are prepared in a crossed (orthogonally oriented) pattern. The corrugation Λ_1 serves for resonant excitation of PSP modes at the inner (substrate) side of the thin Au film via first-order diffraction phase-matching. Cross-coupling of these PSPs through the thin Au film to the outer (sensor) side is achieved by the short-period corrugation Λ_2 . Spectral range where the optical excitation with a normally incident optical beam occurs and the efficiency of the coupling across the thin Au film can be tuned by the design of the periods and respective corrugation amplitudes (as discussed in our previous work [21]). The corrugation profile of the master structure (periods $\Lambda_1=456$ nm and $\Lambda_2= 239$ nm) can be modified upon the replication process and herein we investigated its finetuning for optimum performance for the ACM-SPR.

Topography of the imprinted MPG structure after its coating with Au film was measured with atomic force microscopy (AFM) as shown in Fig. 3a. AFM micrographs were analyzed with fast-Fourier transformation (FFT) to determine the periods and amplitudes of MPG components as presented in Fig. 3b. Interestingly, these data show that the curing condition of the PDMS stamp (performed at room temperature $RT=20-22^\circ\text{C}$ and elevated temperature of 60°C) allows for shifting the periods Λ_1 and Λ_2 without substantially affecting the modulation amplitudes. When the PDMS stamp was cured at room temperature (RT), periods of Λ_1 and Λ_2 matched the values measured for the master. The curing at elevated temperature of 60°C resulted in shorter periods due to the thermal contraction of the PDMS stamp when it was cooled to room temperature RT for the imprinting of MPG. A reduction of the periods $\Delta\Lambda_1 = -8$ nm and $\Delta\Lambda_2 = -7$ nm was evaluated from the data presented in Fig. 3b. These results demonstrate that the UV-NIL replication process can be efficiently controlled to fine-tuning the MPG structure without the necessity of fabricating multiple master substrates.

Fig. 3 a) AFM characterization of MPG topography with b) respective FFT analysis. Comparison of SPR spectra measured for sensor chip with c) tuned MPG periods Λ_1 and Λ_2 upon the imprinting step and d) for varied thickness of Cr layer when the PDMS stamp curing temperature was of 60 °C. The sensor chip was contacted with water $n=1.33$ and reflectivity spectra were measured with normally incident collimated beam ($\theta = 0$).

The impact of tuning the MPG corrugation periods Λ_1 and Λ_2 to its plasmonic properties is assessed by measuring reflectivity spectra $R(\lambda)$ with a collimated normally incident beam ($\theta = 0$). As can be seen in **Fig. 3c**, the excitation of cross-coupled PSP modes exhibit itself as two overlapping Lorentzian dips with minima located at shorter wavelength λ_s (close to 700 nm) and longer wavelength λ_L (in vicinity to 740 nm). The shortening of periods Λ_1 and Λ_2 by curing the PDMS stamp at elevated temperature leads to a weak blue shift of the resonant wavelengths ($\Delta\lambda_s = -1$ nm and $\Delta\lambda_L = -4.5$ nm) and strongly pronounced changes in the coupling strength (represented by the intensities $R(\lambda_s)$ and $R(\lambda_L)$ at respective minima). In particular, the coupling strength evolves in opposite sense at λ_s and λ_L . The depth of the dip at λ_s increases while that at λ_L decreases when shortening the periods Λ_1 and Λ_2 , indicating an anti-crossing nature of the involved SPR resonances on the used plasmonic MPG.

An additional important parameter of the plasmonic MPG is its metallic thin film structure. Strong adhesion of the Au layer to the substrate is essential for maintaining the integrity of the SPR sensor chip over time, a crucial aspect for substrates undergoing further microfabrication steps needed in more complex sensor architectures and when utilized for surface modification in solvents. Even though the chemical composition of the nanoimprint resist (Amonil) promotes the adhesion of Au, it was not sufficient and delamination or cracking of the Au film was observed if the sensor chips are exposed to harsh chemical and/or mechanical stress (see **Fig. S1**). It is very well established that a thin Cr layer, typically 2 nm in thickness, significantly improves the adhesion of Au to the substrate. However, Cr is a very poor plasmonic material due to its high optical damping, which is a drawback for the backside-excitation of PSPs using the investigated MPG structure. The resulting reflectivity spectra $R(\lambda)$ obtained from sensor chips with a Cr adhesion layer thickness between $d_{Cr} = 0$ and 2 nm are shown in **Fig. 3d**. While a thickness of $d_{Cr} = 0.5$ nm showed only minimal improvement in Au adhesion (**Fig. S1**), a 2 nm thick Cr layer almost completely quenched the cross-coupling (by broadening the spectra and shifting the phase-matching condition to a longer wavelength spectral region). A thickness of $d_{Cr} = 1$ nm of the Cr adhesion layer appeared to be an optimum compromise between enhanced Au adhesion and increased damping. In addition, it allowed for balancing the coupling strength to two cross-coupled bands with $R(\lambda_s) \sim R(\lambda_L)$.

3.2 Angular dependence of AMT-SPR

The anti-crossing character of the SPR on developed MPG sensor chip was verified by the measurement of angular dependence of reflectivity spectra $R(\lambda, \theta)$. These spectra were measured for back-coupling to PSPs traveling along the MPG structure contacted with water (refractive index $n=1.330$) and 50 % ethylene glycol (refractive index $n=1.382$). As **Fig. 4a,b** shows, diffraction of PSPs manifests itself as V-shaped dispersion relation for the angles $\theta > 10^\circ$. This behavior is similar to diffraction coupling to PSP on regular periodically corrugated gratings and can be attributed to the first order diffraction phase-matching with PSPs at the inner surface of the Au film (see schematics in **Fig. 4c**) via the MPG component Λ_1 . However, the measured spectra show a different, more complex dependence of $R(\lambda, \theta)$ at short angles $\theta < 10^\circ$. A gap appears in the wavelength range between 750 and 790 nm with an anti-crossing coupling to PSPs in the short wavelength dispersion branch located in wavelength region 700 – 740 nm. The short wavelength branch exhibits two narrow resonances at wavelengths λ_s and λ_L , which weakly shift and swap their coupling strength when increasing refractive index on the top of the MPG surface. In line with the previous observations in **Fig. 3**, increasing the refractive index leads to an enhanced coupling strength to the short

wavelength resonance λ_s and reduced coupling strength to that at λ_L . Importantly, this interaction is weakly dependent on the angle of incidence θ in the range 0-10°, which corresponds to the numerical aperture of 0.17.

Fig. 4 Reflectivity dependence on angle of incidence and wavelength $R(\lambda, \theta)$ for MPG structure contacted with a) water $n=1.330$ and b) with 50 % ethylene glycol $n=1.382$. c) Ratio of the reflectivity spectra $R(n = 1.38)/R(n = 1.33)$. d) Schematics of the used geometry with a light beam impinging on the surface with MPG facilitating a backside excitation of PSP at the outer interface contacted with a liquid sample.

3.3. Signal analysis and calibration

The observed changes in SPR reflectivity spectra were utilized for monitoring of molecular binding-induced refractive index changes with optimized signal-to-noise ratio. In this study, the fiber optic setup was used for the excitation of PSPs by using a diverging light cone emitted from an optical fiber end positioned below the MPG sensor chip. Firstly, a centroid method was tested to quantify changes in the acquired SPR spectra $R(\lambda)$ similar to the previous study [21]. Briefly, a wavelength range $\lambda_{N1} - \lambda_{N2}$ and a threshold R_t were set (**Fig. S2a**) for determining the centroid wavelength from discrete reflectivity values acquired from the spectrometer detector pixels according to Eq. S1 [24]. The outcome of this approach was strongly changing with small variations of parameters λ_{N1} , λ_{N2} , and R_t , which severely hindered the reproducibility of the acquired data. The reason is that the centroid responds in opposite manner to the coupling strength changes and to weak spectral shifts of the bands at λ_s and λ_L . Therefore, another more robust approach was pursued based on PSP mode anti-crossing modulation – ACM. There was exploited the opposite response of reflectivity at λ_s and λ_L to a change of refractive index on the MPG. In the proposed ACM-SPR method, the minimum intensity of the short wavelength dip $R(\lambda_s)$ and longer wavelength dip $R(\lambda_L)$ were determined. In order to reduce the noise, intensity values in the vicinity to the minima positions were

averaged over a range of wavelengths, with an optimum of averaging 100 spectral points (see SI) The SPR output signal was defined as ratio between the averaged intensity values $\bar{R}(\lambda_L)/\bar{R}(\lambda_S)$ (Fig. S2b).

The ACM-SPR response was further calibrated to determine Γ associated with molecular binding events. Therefore, PEMs were assembled using a layer-by-layer approach by alternating exposure of the sensor surface to positively charged PDADMAC and negatively charged PSS polymers (Fig. 5a). Following the deposition of each layer, the spectral response as well as the ACM-SPR response $\bar{R}(\lambda_L)/\bar{R}(\lambda_S)$ was recorded, see Fig. 5b. The same procedure was replicated with a reference fiber optic FO-SPR sensor with the known SPR response per PEM layer [13] to establishing a direct relationship presented in Fig. 5c. The obtained linear fit yielded a correlation factor of $1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ ng}^{-1}$ (R^2 of 0.99) for optimized ACM-SPR chips (fabricated with PDMS working stamps cured at elevated temperature and with a Cr adhesion layer thickness of 1 nm).

Fig. 5 a) Schematic representation of the PEM LbL assembly on the sensor surface. b) Measured SPR spectra changes upon LbL deposition of PSS and PDADMAC polymer multilayer with c) dependence of the sensor output on Γ (for the ACM-SPR sensor chip prepared from a PDMS master casted at elevated temperature of 60 °C and using a 1 nm Cr adhesion layer). The red line corresponds to the linear fit.

3.4 Development of CSPG4 immunoassay

ACM-SPR sensor chips were employed for the establishing of sandwich immunoassays for chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4 (CSPG4), which has been identified as a melanoma cancer biomarker and potential candidate for immunotherapy [30]. The prepared sensor chips were loaded to a dual-channel optical reader system, where the probing of spatially separated sensing spots was performed in parallel with two collimated polychromatic beams (see Fig. 2b). As illustrated in Fig. 6a, sensor chips with an Au layer-coated MPG structure were modified with a mixed thiol SAM bearing antifouling zwitterionic carboxybetaine (CB) and sulfobetaine (SB) headgroups. The composition of CB and SB was set to the ratio 1:4. The carboxyl group in CB thiol served for the covalent attachment of protein molecules *via* amine coupling and a SB carpet was used to repel nonspecific interactions with the surface. Two monoclonal antibodies, Ep2 and Ep3, were tested for affinity binding to the CSPG4 analyte. The herein tested format includes affinity binding of CSPG4 present in the liquid sample to the sensor surface with anchored antibody (see Fig. 6a, channel A) or *vice versa* (see Fig. 6a, channel B), conducted simultaneously on the same sensor chip.

Fig. 6 a) Schematics of the used amine coupling in conjunction with mixed thiol SAM (carboxybetaine (CB) and sulfobetaine (SB)) on the Au surface for the immobilization of antibody Ep3 (channel A) and antigen CSPG4 (channel B). b) SPR-ACM sensorgram of functionalization and affinity interaction between CSPG4 and Ep2,3 antibodies.

The measured sensor responses are presented in **Fig. 6b**. The surface was rinsed with water and PBS, and then carboxylic moieties of the CBs groups were activated by a freshly prepared aqueous mixture of EDC (0.4M) and NHS (0.1M) for 10 min. In the first channel A (upper part of **Fig. 6b**), the Ep3 antibody, dissolved in PBS (125 nM), was flowed over the sensor surface for 10 min. The AMC-SPR sensor response gradually increased due to the covalent coupling of Ep3 to the activated CB groups. Based on the sensor response, a Γ for the coupled Ep3 antibody of $141 \pm 5 \text{ ng cm}^{-2}$ was determined, taking the above-established calibration factor (**Fig. 5c**) into account. By injecting ethanolamine, the excess of the activated CB groups (not reacted with the antibody) were passivated. For the affinity interaction study, PBS was replaced with the working buffer PBS-Tween-BSA to block the surface and further prevent nonspecific binding. CSPG4 (125 nM) was allowed to interact with the Ep3 in two steps with a duration of 20 min. After washing with working buffer PBS-Tween-BSA, the ACM-SPR sensor response for the CSPG4 binding corresponds to a Γ of $305 \pm 11 \text{ ng cm}^{-2}$ for the bound CSPG4. Finally, the Ep2 dissolved in the working buffer (125 nM) was introduced to the sensor and flowed over the sensor surface for 18 min. The measured response indicates,

that Ep2 can bind to the protein on a different specific region compared to the surface-immobilized Ep3. This possibility for a sandwich assay using Ep2 and Ep3 antibodies was further confirmed by an ELISA test (see SI).

In the second channel B (bottom part of **Fig. 6b**), CSPG4 dissolved in PBS (125 nM) was introduced to the surface for 10 min. The ACM-SPR sensor response rapidly increased owing to the covalent coupling with the CB groups. The surface was passivated by injecting ethanolamine, washing off the weakly bound molecules of the sensor surface. The overall larger ACM-SPR response for the CSPG4 coupling to the activated SAM compared to the Ep3 antibody coupling (see channel A) can be ascribed to the difference in molecular weight of CSPG4 (250 kDa) compared to IgG antibodies (150 kDa). The surface-bound CSPG4 resulted in a Γ of $704 \pm 26 \text{ ng cm}^{-2}$. Then, PBS was replaced with the working buffer. Ep3 (125 nM) was injected to interact with the CSPG4 in two steps with a duration of 20 min. After washing with the working buffer, the ACM-SPR sensor response to Ep3 binding corresponds to a Γ of $176 \pm 7 \text{ ng cm}^{-2}$. Finally, the Ep2, dissolved in the working buffer (125 nM), was flowed over the sensor surface for 18 min. Similarly to channel A, the measured response in channel B shows that Ep2 can recognize the protein CSPG4 from its specific paratope region.

Fig. 7 Comparison of SPR-ACM and regular SPR biosensor with spectral interrogation for a) the signal of CSPG4 coupling to the EDC/NHS activated SAM (inset shows a zoom-in of the noise level), b) the obtained signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio for the CSPG4 coupling, and c) the refractive index resolution.

The accuracy of the reported ACM-SPR approach was compared with the regular implementation of an ATR-based biosensor with wavelength interrogation of SPR. The ATR-based SPR instrument was configured to probe a flat Au sensor surface with resonantly excited PSPs at a similar wavelength of 670 nm. The sensor output was measured with the same optical components including light source, input and output optical fibers, spectrometers, and microfluidic device. **Fig. 7a** compares the sensor responses for the covalent coupling of the CSPG4 protein to the mixed thiol SAM. Both sensorgrams show a similar profile of the CSPG4 binding kinetics, with a slightly higher overall signal for the calibrated ACM-SPR response. However, the higher noise level obtained for the ACM-SPR approach results in a reduced, yet still comparable, signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio for the CSPG4 coupling compared to the regular, ATR-based biosensor with wavelength interrogation of SPR (**Fig. 7b**). Even though the regular ATR SPR provided slightly better refractive index resolution (**Fig. 7c**), the ACM-SPR approach presents similar performance while allowing the use of simplified optical components. Thus, we believe that the developed sensor chip

holds great potential for a broad range of sensing applications, particularly in the context of point-of-care diagnostics.

Conclusions

In summary, we have devised a versatile approach to direct label-free SPR biosensing based on tailored multiperiodic plasmonic grating (MPG) supporting cross-coupled PSP modes. It allows for diffraction-based backside excitation of PSP and an implementation with fiber optic SPR system and in a configuration compatible with regular prism biosensor with wavelength interrogation of SPR is demonstrated. This approach is suitable for simplified evaluation of sensor response referred as to anti-crossing modulation (ACM) of SPR, which relies on monitoring of intensity ratio of two neighboring absorption bands in the wavelength spectrum. This type of evaluation may be in future carried out based on two bandpass filters without the need of using a spectrometer. The implementation of ACM-SPR is discussed in terms of fine-tuning the MPG structure, its sensitivity to bulk refractive index changes as well as surface mass density variations. The potential of ACM-SPR for biomolecular affinity interaction studies is demonstrated through an experiment where the implementation of sandwich CSPG4 immunoassay is investigated in connection to self-assembled biointerfaces with zwitterionic headgroups. The obtained results revealed a possibility to form sandwich with the use of monoclonal antibodies Ep2 and Ep3 and allowed for quantifying the molecular binding ratios.

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